

Research paper

**No one knows what infinity is and the truth
about the sum of positive numbers.
(The first review of the myths of some mathematicians)**

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I present this research paper as a gift to all universities in the world.
And personally, for these universities

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Abstract:

For my work as a mathematics teacher, I am exposed to many questions from students about some mathematical rules and how to prove them. One day, one of the students stopped me during the lesson to ask me about the sum of the positive integers to infinity. He said that he had watched a video on YouTube that said that the sum of the positive integers is a negative number and equals $-1/12$. I watched the video and the proof of addition of integers, and I am sorry to say that I tried to convince myself of this proof, but to no avail. Therefore, I wrote this research paper that discusses all the errors of scientists regarding the truth of addition of positive integers. And out of my belief that all universities around the world are beacons of knowledge, I put up some university logos to review my research paper. I also ask all universities around the world to protect future generations from some of the myths and false information that appear today on all social media platforms, which create a kind of ignorance among specialists. In certain fields and to non-specialists, I express my regret to all universities for using their logos without permission. Thank you very much.

INTRODUCTION:

As we know, Sir Ramanujan gave the solution of sum of all natural numbers up to infinity and said that the sum of all natural numbers till infinity is $-1/12$. I studied on this topic and found that if we try to solve the infinite series in a slightly different way, then we get the answer of its sum different from $-1/12$, so this is what I have written in this paper that such Ramanujan Sir, what was the mistake in solving the infinite series, which by solving it in a slightly different way from the same concept, we get different answers

1- The first error of the theory of the sum of all positive numbers:

If you have sequence $w = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, \dots\}$

We can write it like this $w = \{n_1, n_2, n_3, n_4, n_5, n_6, \dots\}$

And we all know about the basic laws of inequality and all students in primary, middle, and high school study them.

If you have four values a, b, c, d where $a < b$, $c < d$ so $a + b < c + d$

By applying this rule to the previous sequence, we find that.

$$n_1 < n_2 < n_3 < n_4 < n_5 < \dots$$

$$\text{so } n_1 + n_2 < n_3 + n_4 \quad \text{and } n_1 + n_2 < n_3 + n_4 + n_5$$

$$\text{and } n_1 + n_2 < n_3 + n_4 + n_5 + \dots$$

$$\text{So } n_1 < n_1 + n_2 + n_3 + n_4 + n_5 + \dots$$

So $n_1 < \sum_{i=1}^{\infty}(n_i)$ this means that the sum of all positive numbers cannot be less than one.

If what was mentioned previously is wrong and the sum of all positive numbers is less than one, this means that everything we teach to our students at all educational levels is wrong.

2- The second error of the theory of the sum of all positive numbers:

Let us believe that the sum of all positive numbers is equal to $\frac{-1}{12}$ and I hope all readers believe this temporarily and I will also try to believe that with you.

If you read mathematics books for high school students, you find that they have a unit that talks about sequences and series and all mathematics books around the world have this unit, and I will quote for you, dear readers, from this unit (SUMMATION OF SERIES).

The rule says, "Sum of the first n natural numbers."

$$1+2+3+4+5+\dots+n = \frac{n(n+1)}{2}$$

$$\text{If the sum of all positive numbers} = \frac{-1}{12}$$

$$\text{So } \frac{n(n+1)}{2} = \frac{-1}{12} \rightarrow n(n+1) = \frac{-1}{6} \rightarrow n^2 + n = \frac{-1}{6} \rightarrow 6n^2 + 6n + 1 = 0$$

When solving this equation, we find two solutions to the equation.

$$n_1 = \frac{-1}{2} - \frac{\sqrt{3}}{6} = -0.78867513459 = -788.67513459 \times 10^{-3}$$

$$n_2 = \frac{-1}{2} + \frac{\sqrt{3}}{6} = -0.21132486541 = -211.32486541 \times 10^{-3}$$

When you see these values, what do you expect these values to be? And I tell you directly that values are supposed to be the largest positive number in the universe. You can imagine that from your vision of the result, which I deliberately wrote in three ways of clarification if someone insists that these values are normal values for the equation, let us continue and find the general term in this sequence and the method of calculating it is as follows.

nth Term of an AP Sequence is a Linear Expression of n.

Let the first term is a and the common difference is d of an AP. Then

$$t_n = a + (n - 1) d$$

$$a = 1 \quad n = \frac{-1}{2} - \frac{\sqrt{3}}{6} \quad d = 1$$

$$t_n = 1 + \left(\frac{-1}{2} - \frac{\sqrt{3}}{6} - 1 \right) \times 1 = \frac{-1}{2} - \frac{\sqrt{3}}{6} = -0.78867513459$$

(If you watch the result, you will find yourself returning to the same point)

Quite simply, the result shown in front of you explains one thing to you, which is that the scientists who created this sum for all positive numbers did not sum the positive numbers at all and this number appearing in front of you is supposed to be the order of the largest term in the positive numbers. What a big joke??!

3- The third error of the theory of the sum of all positive numbers:

There are two proofs for the sum of positive integers that are supposed to have been developed by specialists in the field of mathematics, but which one is correct? This is the problem. We will now review the two proofs.

First proof:

We assume that we have a series S.

$$s = 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 + 10 + 11 + \dots$$

$$s = 1 + (2 + 3 + 4) + (5 + 6 + 7) + (8 + 9 + 10) + (11 + 12 + 13) \dots$$

$$s = 1 + 9 + 18 + 27 + 36 + 45 + 54 + 63 + 72 + \dots$$

$$s = 1 + 9(1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 + \dots)$$

$$s = 1 + 9s \rightarrow -8s = 1$$

$$\rightarrow s = \frac{-1}{8} \quad \rightarrow \text{the sum of all positive numbers} = \frac{-1}{8}$$

Second proof:

Ramanujan summation

$$\text{Let } S_1 = 1+2+3+4+5+6+\dots \quad \text{Equation (1)}$$

$$S_2 = 1-1+1-1+1-1+\dots \quad \text{Equation (2)}$$

On writing the terms of equation (2) leaving one space from the beginning

$$S_2 = 1 - (1-1+1-1+1-1+\dots)$$

$$S_2 = 1 - (S_2)$$

$$2 S_2 = 1$$

$$S_2 = \frac{1}{2}$$

$$\text{Let } S_3 = 1-2+3-4+5-6+\dots \quad \text{Equation (3)}$$

Subtract Equation (3) from Equation (2)

$$(S_2 - S_3) = 0+1-2+3-4+5+\dots$$

$$(S_2 - S_3) = S_3$$

$$2 S_3 = S_2$$

$$S_3 = \frac{S_2}{2}$$

$$S_3 = \frac{1}{4}$$

Subtract Equation (3) from Equation (1)

$$(S_1 - S_3) = 4 + 8 + 12 + 16 + 20 + 24 \dots$$

$$(S_1 - S_3) = 4(1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + \dots)$$

$$(S_1 - S_3) = 4 S_1$$

$$3S_1 = - S_3$$

$$3S_1 = -\frac{1}{4}$$

$$S_1 = \frac{-1}{12}$$

$$\text{So } \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n = -\frac{1}{12}$$

Analysis:

After presenting the two proofs, dear reader, you will find that there is a difference between the two results. The first proof gives a value, and the second proof gives a different value. In the opinion of many of the public and some scholars, both are correct, but in your opinion, which is more correct, the first or the second? From my point of view and through my research, both proofs are just an illusion and a myth. They do not represent anything of science. They are merely fraud and belittling the minds of the general public. In this research paper, I will present to you what is wrong with these two proofs, what is their problem, and how they have violated some important mathematical rules that cannot be ignored or belittled because they are the foundations of ancient and modern mathematics. With these foundations, we would be in a major clash, as happened with us now in this issue, which is the issue of the sum of positive integers.

Double standards discussion

You will know why I named this title when you read next.

In principle, if the sum of all positive integers is $-1/12$, is it assumed that when any number is excluded from the series, the sum changes or remains the same? This is an important question. We now begin to test it.

$$\text{Let } S_1 = 1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+10+\dots \text{ Equation (1)}$$

$$\text{And } S_2 = 1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+\dots \text{ Equation (2)}$$

Subtract (S2) from (S1)

$$(S_1 - S_2) = 0+1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+10+\dots\dots\dots \text{Equation (3)}$$

Since zero is Additive identity element, we reformulate the equation to become:

$$\text{So } (S_1 - S_2) = S_1 = 1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+10+\dots\dots\dots \text{Equation (3)}$$

Repeat the process again.

Subtract Equation (2) from Equation (3)

$$(S_1 - S_2) - S_2 = 0+1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+10+\dots\dots\dots \text{Equation (4)}$$

Since zero is Additive identity element, we reformulate the equation to become:

$$\text{So } (S_1 - 2S_2) = S_1 = 1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+10+\dots\dots\dots \text{Equation (4)}$$

Repeat the process again.

Subtract Equation (2) from Equation (4)

$$\text{So } (S_1 - 2S_2) - S_2 = 0+1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+10+\dots\dots\dots \text{Equation (5)}$$

Since zero is Additive identity element, we reformulate the equation to become:

$$\text{So } (S_1 - 3S_2) = S_1 = 1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+10+\dots\dots\dots \text{Equation (5)}$$

Repeat the process again.

Subtract Equation (2) from Equation (5)

$$\text{So } (S_1 - 3S_2) - S_2 = 0+1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+10+\dots\dots\dots \text{Equation (6)}$$

Since zero is Additive identity element, we reformulate the equation to become:

$$\text{So } (S_1 - 4S_2) = S_1 = 1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+10+\dots\dots\dots \text{Equation (6)}$$

Repeat the process again.

Subtract Equation (2) from Equation (6)

$$\text{So } (S_1 - 4S_2) - S_2 = 0+1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+10+\dots\dots\dots \text{Equation (7)}$$

Since zero is Additive identity element, we reformulate the equation to become:

$$\text{So } (S_1 - 5S_2) = S_1 = 1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+10+\dots\dots\dots \text{Equation (7)}$$

From here we deduce an important rule from all the operations mentioned above, which is as follows:

$$(S_1 - nS_2) = S_1 = 1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+10+\dots = \frac{-1}{12}$$

Where n is a positive integer greater than zero

If you look at the proof mentioned above, you will find that we have deduced an important rule, which is what you see in the rectangle. When reading this proof, the readers will be divided into two parts: the first part believes this proof and sees that it is beyond doubt, and the second part denies this result, but how can it be proven that it is not true? This is the problem, so I will make a simple change. This will make it clear to you with this simple example. Ask one of your students to solve this example that I will put in front of you.

Example:

Let $S_1 = 1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+10+\dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n = -\frac{1}{12}$

And $S_2 = 1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+\dots$

Find the value of $(S_1 - 5S_2)$

Solution:

If $S_2 = 1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+\dots$

So $5S_2 = 5+5+5+5+5+5+5+5+5+5+\dots$

So $(S_1 - 5S_2) = -4 - 3 - 2 - 1 + 0 + 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + \dots$

If we eliminate the negative terms from this series, the result is:

$(S_1 - 5S_2) = 0 + 0 + 0 + 0 + 0 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 + 10 + \dots$

Since zero is Additive identity element, we reformulate the equation to become:

$(S_1 - 5S_2) = 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 + 10 + \dots = \sum_{n=5}^{\infty} n$

$(S_1 - 5S_2) = \sum_{n=5}^{\infty} (n) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (n) - \sum_{n=1}^4 (n) = \frac{-1}{12} - (1 + 2 + 3 + 4) = \frac{-1}{12} - 10$

$(S_1 - 5S_2) = \frac{-1}{12} - 10 = \frac{-121}{12} = -10.08333333333333$

If you look at the solution to the example, you will find that the student reached a result that you did not expect. If you give the student the same result that he reached

and ask him to find the series S_1 , you will find another result that you did not expect. Here you ask yourself, dear reader, what happens and why are all these differences? The answer to this question is that everything we did, in terms of deducing a rule, solving an example, and applying the rule to the example, contained blatant errors and violated general rules that cannot be underestimated. This is the problem of all mathematicians who tried to find the sum of all positive integers. Everyone who tried to prove that positive integers up to infinity have a sum has committed major errors in all their results. Look now, dear reader, at this example that I will present to you now, and you will know the extent of the mistakes that some scholars made.

Now ask the same student to solve this example.

Example 2:

$$\text{Let } (S_1 - 5S_2) = 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 + 10 + \dots = \sum_{n=5}^{\infty} n$$

$$\text{And } S_2 = 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + \dots$$

Find the series S_1

Solution:

$$\text{If } (S_1 - 5S_2) = 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 + 10 + \dots = \sum_{n=5}^{\infty} n$$

$$\text{So } S_1 = (5S_2) + (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 + 10 + \dots)$$

$$S_1 = (5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + \dots) + (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 + 10 + \dots)$$

$$S_1 = 10 + 11 + 12 + 13 + 14 + 15 + 16 + \dots = \sum_{n=10}^{\infty} n$$

This means that.

$$S_1 = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n - \sum_{n=1}^9 n$$

This result is a value that is contrary to the value of the original series that was imposed in our first proof. What I want to say is that there were major violations that occurred while developing the proof, imposing the law, and applying the law in the first example, and trying to find the value of the original series in the second example, which is what I call a new concept. (Double standards discussion) My definition of this concept is as follows:

Double standards discussion

I developed this term for any issue or scientific proof that has caused great controversy among scholars or the public. This term works as follows:

- 1- Develop a hypothesis that is like the disputed hypothesis and matches it in style, pattern and standard
- 2- Inferring a rule that is like the rule over which there is disagreement, while replicating any strategy within the rule over which there is disagreement
- 3- Provide an example of applying the new rule to it
- 4- Make a simple change within the example to test the stability of the rule
- 5- Trying to use the rule in reverse to return to the original example
- 6- If there is a significant difference between the results of these stages, this is evidence of the lack of credibility of the hypothesis upon which the dispute is made
- 7- If there is agreement between the results of the previous stages, this is evidence of the stability of the hypothesis over which there is disagreement

Results:

There are general rules agreed upon by many scholars. If these rules are transgressed, blatant and unimaginable mistakes will occur. These rules include the following:

- 1- Every series has a known limit. The result of this series can be found with ease if the first and last terms exist and the difference between the terms of the series are fixed known values.
- 2- Any process of adding numbers follows an important element, which is time. It is not possible to perform an addition or subtraction process without placing the time factor as a basic factor.
- 3- If a specific symbol is placed to express a finite series with a known end, this symbol represents the value of the series
- 4- If a specific symbol is used to express an infinite series (the end is unknown), then this symbol represents only the name of the series and does not represent its value. Therefore, when expressing any series that does not end with a symbol, this symbol is just a name and not a value, if the final value of the last term is unknown, this symbol remains just a name.
- 5- Infinity is an abstract definition of a number that cannot be perceived if the time element is unlimited
- 6- If you were given a result of the sum of the positive integers, your first question would be: What is the time required to find the sum of these numbers?

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